

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

STRUCTURE OF SARS-COV-2 AND MEDICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF PROTEINS

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the structural structure of the SARS-CoV-2 virus, studying its pathogenetic properties, analyzing the role of the immune system, as well as the disorders it causes in the human body. In early December 2019, the first cases of pneumonia of unknown origin were identified in Wuhan, Hubei Province, China. The SARS-CoV-2 coronavirus is a characteristic enveloped RNA-containing virus with "crown"-shaped processes, the main structural proteins of which are the nucleocapsid protein and the receptor-binding transmembrane protein S, which causes infection of epithelial cells of the respiratory tract mucosa. Both proteins are considered highly immunogenic antigens for humans. C-19 hyperinflammation can cause cytopenia, coagulopathy, tissue damage, liver dysfunction and macrophage activation, vasculitis, and sepsis. Also, excessive production of cytokines can lead to multiple organ failure and eventually death. Based on the results of the research, we decided that the role of structural molecules in the pathogenesis of coronavirus infection is important, and people who received the vaccine produced against this virus experienced this disease more easily and recovered quickly. In the treatment of this pathology, the use of components of vaccines and promising ligands is appropriate.

Keywords: SARS-CoV-2 coronavirus, immunogenic antigens, cytokines, vaccines, immune system.

INTRODUCTION

Any molecule that can be specifically recognized by elements of the immune system (T and B cells) has antigenic properties. It is known that B cells need the help of T cells to produce specific antibodies. Helper T cells bind specifically to antigen-presenting cells. Although conventional antigen-presenting cells such as macrophages do not exhibit antigen (Ag) binding specificity, B cells have clonally distributed antigen-specific surface immunoglobulin receptors [19].

PURPOSE

It consists of studying the role and importance of SARS-CoV-2 coronavirus proteins and applying them in medicine.

CLASSIFICATION OF ANTIGENS

According to their origin, 3 types of antigens (Ag) are distinguished. Ags that enter the human body from the environment are exoantigens. These are endoantigens, which are formed during metabolic or pathological processes in the body. Autoantigens are the body's normal proteins that are recognized as antigens by the immune system as a result of exposure to environmental factors or autoimmune diseases. Some Ags can cause massive non-specific activation of T-lymphocytes, called Superantigens (SAGs).

Figure 1. Schematic of Superantigens that activate T cells

Currently, all SAGs produced by pathogenic microorganisms (bacteria, mycoplasmas) and viruses known in nature are protein-containing [27], and they differ from all other agents in that they activate free T cells without preprocessing on the surface of antigen-presenting cells. SAGs bind directly to the T-cell receptor (TCR) and histocompatibility complex-II (HCC-II) receptor outside the normal antigen-binding site, thereby bypassing antigen processing (Figure 1).

SAGs recognize antigens by simultaneously attracting antigen-presenting HCC-II molecules on the cell surface and the TCR on the T-cell surface. The antigen located in such a related HCC-II complex is of no importance, at which time non-specific activation of β -subunit cells with a type of T-cell receptor on its surface occurs. Thus, a superantigen can induce the activation of 2-20% of all T cells. Most of these cells are usually (CD4+) T helper cells, which secrete large amounts of cytokines. Excess cytokines lead to systemic toxicity and suppression of the adaptive immune response beneficial to the pathogen [27]. In the initial phase of the

immune response, activated T cells release IL-2, INF- γ , and TNF- α . This is followed by the activation of macrophage-produced cytokines - IL-1, IL-6, IL-8 and TNF- α , chemokines, leukotrienes, prostaglandins and complement proteins. All of these, in severe cases, lead to vasodilation and extravasation of fluid from the vessels, resulting in tissue hypoperfusion, shock, and multiple organ failure.

VIRUS STRUCTURE

The C-19 virus belongs to the order Nidovirales, family Coronaviridae, and subfamily Orthocoronavirinae, and consists of surface proteins, capsid proteins, and RNA. Coronaviruses have single-stranded, positively charged RNA and have one of the largest genomes of RNA viruses. At the 5' end, two-thirds of the coronavirus genome encodes viral proteins involved in viral RNA transcription and replication, and at the 3' end, one-third encodes additional proteins related to structure and group. The main structural proteins of coronaviruses are S (spike), E (envelope), M (membrane) and N (nucleocapsid) (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Structural proteins of the coronavirus

These biomarkers play a central role not only in disease diagnosis but also in understanding its pathogenesis [13].

SPIKE PROTEIN (S protein)

Before binding to the cell membrane, the S protein is usually in a metastable conformation. After the virus interacts with the host cell, an extensive structural rearrangement of the S protein occurs, allowing the virus to fuse with the host cell membrane. When the S protein

penetrates the cell, it is coated with polysaccharide molecules to prevent the host's immune response [29]. S protein trimers visually form a characteristic onion-shaped crown surrounding the viral particle. During viral infection, proteases of target cells cleave the S protein into S₁ (Fig 3) and S₂ proteins [4], which is necessary to activate the membrane fusion site for virus penetration into target cells [16, 10].

Figure 3. Structural scheme of SARS-CoV-2 S protein

ENVELOPE PROTEIN (E protein)

E protein is a small hydrophobic protein consisting of 74-109 amino acids. Molecular weight 8.4-109 kDa. It consists of three parts: an N-terminal domain (NTD), a transmembrane domain (TMD) anchored to the viral membrane, and a short intracellular C-terminal domain (CTD) [14]. In the structure of E protein, there are three cysteine sites characteristic of palmitoylated protein [20, 26]. Although the exact function of the palmitoylated protein is still controversial, research into the protein's role in coronavirus disease is ongoing. Alterations of all three amino acids in MHV-CoV can significantly attenuate the virus [21]. Another conserved amino acid in the E protein structure is β -coil- β . It plays an important role in protein folding in the Golgi complex [26]. E protein forms an ion channel in the cell, increases the activity of viroporin, participates in the assembly of viruses, and also mediates the exocytosis of virus particles [24], and plays an important role in pathogenicity [17].

MATRIX PROTEIN (M protein)

Recent studies have shown that M proteins of SARS-CoV-2 are 39.2 and 90.1% identical to M proteins of MERS-CoV and SARS-CoV, respectively [2]. M protein is a transmembrane glycoprotein and an important structural protein of coronaviruses [3]. It is the most abundant protein on the surface of the virus and gives it its shape. According to studies on the two viruses SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV, the M protein consists of 230 amino acids has a molecular weight of 25-35 kDa and is the smallest structural protein of SARS-CoV-2. In silico analysis revealed that the structure of the SARS-CoV-2 M protein is similar to the prokaryotic glucose transporter protein and has a triple helix bundle and a single TMD.

NUCLEOPROTEIN (N protein)

The nucleoproteins of the coronavirus are localized in the cytoplasm and subnuclear structure both in primary cells infected with the virus and in cells transformed with plasmids expressing the N protein. The molecular weight of N protein is 43-50 kDa. This structural protein of helical nucleocapsid has an affinity for RNA (Fig 4) and several amino acids [6].

Figure 4. The structure of RNA, the structural protein of the helical nucleocapsid

The structure of N protein includes NTD, and CTD, as well as many disordered fragments [18]. The N protein functions to integrate and assemble the viral RNA genome into the long helical structure of the nucleocapsid or ribonucleoprotein matrix; however, it is highly sensitive to proteases [22]. This protein is phosphorylated at several specific positions in different coronaviruses, which leads to changes in its functions, such as specificity for viral RNA, binding of monoclonal antibodies to the surface of the virus, maturation and assembly of the virus [15]. The N protein can also participate in the regulation of viral transcription and increase the efficiency of genomic RNA replication in reverse genetics systems [7].

ANTIGENIC CHARACTERISTICS OF STRUCTURAL PROTEINS OF SARS-COV-2 VIRUS

The M protein is a unique glycoprotein that differs from all other viral glycoproteins in its structural and biological properties. Several studies have shown that the M protein can induce an immune response even when it is largely embedded in the viral membrane [11].

Although the antigenic sites in the M protein have not been identified, its N-terminal hydrophilic ectodomain is believed to contain major antigenic determinants responsible for immunological responses [23]. Wang and co-authors [28] tested peptides derived from several synthetic M proteins for immunoreactivity with serum samples from SARS-CoV-2 patients and showed that they reacted weakly with a short peptide similar to the C-terminal epitope. Because the SARS-CoV N protein has similar antigenic properties and high sequence similarity to other coronavirus N proteins, the full-length N protein may cross-react with antibodies against other coronavirus N proteins, limiting the use of SARS-CoV-2 N. The E protein has multiple functions at different stages of infection. Despite the presence of relatively few copies in each viral particle, it acts as an immunostimulator. Phylogenetic analysis of E protein sequences shows that bat and pangolin coronaviruses are most similar to SARS-CoV-2. Other studies have tested experimentally identified SARS-CoV S protein epitopes and identified corresponding sequences in SARS-CoV-2 [1].

A similar strategy was used in a study by A. Grifoni [14]. Although the S protein of SARS-CoV-2 is 77.38% identical to the S protein of SARS-CoV, most antibodies against the S protein of SARS-CoV showed

weak cross-reactivity with the S protein of SARS-CoV-2 [25] which indicates that the S SARS-CoV-2 protein has a significantly altered structure.

Figure 5. Vaccines using viral proteins

During bioinformatics studies of the S protein of SARS-CoV-2, an amino acid sequence with antigenic properties was discovered. Peptide S 333-338 has high antigenic activity. Note that this peptide is located in the RBD S protein of SARS-CoV-2 [32]. Likely, antibodies that recognize this epitope can also neutralize the virus and prevent infection. Currently, more than 180 vaccines (Fig.5) have been developed against SARS-CoV-2 using viral proteins based on different platforms [9]. Inactivated vaccines of SARS-CoV-2 grown in Vero cells followed by chemical inactivation of the virus [12] are easily produced [8]. Inactivated vaccines include several vaccines developed by Sinovac Biotech in China, as well as by Bharat Biotech in India and Biosafety Research Institute in Kazakhstan, which are convenient and safe for intramuscular administration [30, 31].

Other vaccines are live-attenuated vaccines, which produce a genetically weakened version of the virus that replicates to a limited extent without causing disease but produces an immune response similar to that produced by a natural infection. An important advantage of these vaccines is that they can be administered intranasally, which activates immune responses in the mucous membranes that protect the upper respiratory tract, which is the main portal of entry of the virus. Furthermore, as the virus replicates in the vaccinated individual, the immune response targets both structural and non-structural viral proteins through antibody and cellular immune responses. These vaccines were developed in collaboration between Codagenix and Serum Institute of India [5].

CONCLUSION

Analysis of literature data revealed that all structural proteins of SARS-CoV-2 have antigenic properties. Since the S protein determines the entry of the virus into the cell after binding the ACE2 receptor, we have seen that the S protein of SARS-CoV-2 is a key factor in the pathogenesis of COVID-19 and generates a persistent immune response. Protein S is considered promising in the development of specific peptide ligands. Also, vaccines against SARS-CoV-2 have been developed based on epitopes in the S protein, and intramuscular, intranasal use of these vaccines is considered easier and safer.

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